

Comparison of Measured and Predicted Bistatic Scattering from a Right-Angle Dihedral

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Abstract—The bistatic radar cross section of a dihedral at three different orientations is measured and compared to five scattering predictions—method of moments (MoM), finite integration technique (FIT), shooting and bouncing rays (SBR), and two analytic models—closed-form PO (CPO) and a simplified parametric model. For many applications, accurate predictions in the mainlobe response are of most importance. We show that bistatic CPO and PM predictions have good fit to measured data in the mainlobe and are computationally more efficient than the numerical prediction methods.

Index Terms—dihedral, bistatic scattering, radar cross section

I. INTRODUCTION

Dihedral scattering mechanisms are commonly found in nature and man-made structures, to include landscapes; tree, building, and car interfaces with the ground; and interior building walls. The monostatic dihedral response has been comprehensively studied [1], [2], and analytic solutions are given in [3], [4]. However, bistatic antenna configurations are needed to capture specular returns for real-world 3D geometries. Bistatic scattering is typically predicted using numerical methods, such as method of moments (MoM), finite integration technique (FIT), and shooting and bouncing rays (SBR). Recently, [5] and [6] have proposed computationally efficient analytic models to predict 3D bistatic scattering from a right-angle dihedrals. The model in [5] is a closed-form physical optics (CPO) solution, while the model in [6] is a simplified parametric model (PM) based on principle plane scattering. We compare the MoM, FIT, SBR, CPO, and PM predictions to data measured in the AFIT indoor range facility. We show that all of the prediction methods are accurate in the mainlobe response. Thus, for applications in which mainlobe scattering is of most importance, the computationally efficient CPO and PM methods are best.

II. PREDICTION METHODS

The MoM, FIT, SBR, CPO, PM, and range measurement methods are briefly described.

A. Method of Moments

The method of moments is a numerical technique to solve for target surface current J_s and the associated scattered (re-radiated) fields. The surface current is induced on the target by the transmitted electromagnetic (EM) field. Using EM

boundary conditions and assuming linear, homogeneous and isotropic media, one may define electric and magnetic field integral equations to relate the incident field to a surface integral containing J_s [7]. The MoM technique discretizes the integral equations over a target surface mesh and solves the resulting system of equations to obtain the surface current. Then the associated scattered field is computed. In general, MoM is highly accurate when the mesh size is adequately small ($\approx \lambda/10$) and is excellent at predicting scattering from planar perfect electrical conductor (PEC) targets, such as the dihedral [8]. However, MoM techniques have significant computational time and storage requirements.

B. Finite Integration Technique

FIT is another numerical technique. FIT predicts the scattered EM field by first discretizing and solving Maxwell's integral equations on an overlapping volume grid [9]. The field solution that results is defined in the near field, which therefore defines J_s , allowing the far-field scattering to be calculated. FIT can be used in either the frequency or time domain and to solve problems with non-uniform material properties such as anisotropy and non-linearity. In general for curved three-dimensional targets, the volume mesh used in FIT allows for more accurate results when compared to a surface mesh approach used in MoM. As with MoM, field solution accuracy increases with more dense spatial sampling; this relation is a driving factor in FIT's relatively high computational requirements for planar targets.

C. Shooting and Bouncing Ray

The shooting and bouncing ray (SBR) technique combines geometrical optics (GO) and physical optics (PO) theory to numerically predict the scattered EM field. A collection of parallel rays in the transmit direction are traced as they reflect off the target. The field for each ray is computed using GO, and PO is used to find the induced surface current and field contribution from the last reflection point on the target [10]. The field contributions from each ray are summed in the far-field to find the total scattered field. SBR is more computationally efficient than MoM and FIT; the main computational burden of SBR lies in the ray tracing.

D. Closed-form PO

The theory behind the closed-form PO solution is the same as for SBR, but it is an analytical solution [5]. First-order scattering is found by analytically solving the PO integral over each dihedral plate. Second-order scattering terms are derived by analytically solving the PO integral on the illuminated region of the second plate, where geometric optics is used to define the illuminated region. First and second-order terms are added obtain the final CPO prediction.

E. Parametric Model

Parametric models provide a simplified analytic scattering prediction that is a function of relevant object and antenna parameters. The dihedral PM in [6] is a function of the dihedral location, orientation, and size as well as the transmitter and receiver aspect angles and frequency. PMs are much more computationally efficient than numerical prediction methods but may be less accurate due to approximations used to derive compact PM equations. For example, the dihedral PM in [6] approximates 3D bistatic scattering by calculating the product of a two-dimensional right-angle response (parameterized by antenna elevation angle) with a two-dimensional flat plate response (parameterized by antenna azimuth angle). It is shown in [6] that the PM agrees with SBR predictions near the specular mainlobe response. Due to their compact mathematical representation PMs are useful for signal exploitation applications that try to match measured data to scattering responses of interest [11].

F. Bistatic Indoor Range Facility

The experimental setup in the AFIT bistatic indoor range facility is shown in Figure 1. The target is located on a pedestal in the center of the range. The transmit antenna position is fixed, and the receive antenna moves in a circle around the target. The target pedestal is rotated to achieve a transmitter azimuth aspect angle of ϕ_t . The receive azimuth ϕ_r varies as the receive antenna moves. For this study, the transmit and receive antenna elevation angles are $\theta_t = \theta_r = 0^\circ$. Target roll-pitch-yaw orientation may be varied through the rotation of the pedestal and use of electromagnetically-transparent target mounts. (We define roll, pitch, and yaw as the right-handed rotations about the x , y , and z axes, respectively.) Finally, this facility allows for co-polarization transmit and receive measurements, where HH-polarization refers to the transmit and receive electric field parallel to the ground plane and VV-polarization indicates an electric field perpendicular to the ground plane.

III. MEASUREMENTS AND ANALYSIS

We collect dihedral measurements for three scenarios described in the following subsection. We also compute scattering predictions from the methods described in Section II. We compare each prediction to the measured dihedral response. HH-polarization figures are provided in this section, VV-polarization figures are provided at the end of this document.

Fig. 1. Bistatic indoor range facility experiment setup.

Fig. 2. Dihedral orientations for measurement scenarios are (a) 45° forward pitch (b) 20° forward pitch (c) 20° roll.

A. Measurements

We collect measurements for a metal dihedral target consisting of two 3” by 6” by 0.25” thick metal plates attached to form a right-angle dihedral. The measurement scenarios are listed in Table I and include three target orientations (shown in Figure 2). All measurements are collected at 10 GHz frequency. We calibrate the range measurements using the standard RCS calibration equation [12] and a calibration cylinder. For these measurements, we find the calibration error to be 0.055 dB (HH-pol) and -0.167 dB (VV-pol).

TABLE I
TEST MATRIX

Scenario	Dihedral Orientation	ϕ_t	ϕ_r	$\Delta\phi_r$
S1	45° pitch	-30°	[-22.5°, 70°]	1°
S2	20° pitch	-10°	[-10°, 90°]	1°
S3	20° roll	-30°	[-30°, 70°]	1°

B. Analysis

The HH-polarization measured and predicted scattering response for scenario S1 with dihedral at 45° pitch, $\phi_t = -30^\circ$ and $f = 10$ GHz is shown in Figure 3a. As we expect, the peak response is located at $\phi_r = 30^\circ$. Visual inspection confirms that all prediction methods have similar amplitude and mainlobe width near the peak forward scatter response. Also, at receive angles $< 20^\circ$, the sinc-like diffraction behavior has higher peaks and lower nulls than for angles past the specular response (i.e. $> 40^\circ$). This is because diffraction from the quarter-inch thick front edge of the dihedral is stronger than diffraction produced from the traveling wave energy diffracted from the trailing edge.

The error, defined as

$$\epsilon = \left| 20 \log_{10} \frac{|\text{measured}|}{|\text{predicted}|} \right| \quad (1)$$

is shown in Figure 3b. Visually, we see that all five error waveforms are very similar, especially near the peak forward scatter response. As we expect, the simple SBR, CPO and PM predictions begin to diverge from the measured data outside of the first null, and are significantly different for $\phi_r < 20^\circ$. This is because diffraction from the quarter inch dihedral side is significant in these regions, which these intentionally simple models do not account for.

Fig. 3. (a) Measured and predicted RCS, (b) prediction error for dihedral at 45° pitch, $\phi_t = -30^\circ$ (S1), frequency 10 GHz, HH-polarization.

The HH-polarization scattering response for the dihedral at 20° pitch and $\phi_t = -10^\circ$ (S2) is shown in Fig. 4a. The forward scattering response peaks as we expect at $\phi_r = 10^\circ$. Again, all six responses are fairly similar, especially within the forward scattering mainlobe. However, the FIT prediction's peak response is slightly higher than the MoM waveform in HH-polarization. Measured data inaccuracies exist near the left side of the mainlobe at $\phi_r = 0^\circ$. This behavior was repeatable over many measurement attempts and is most likely caused

by a small physical inconsistency on the dihedral surface. The HH-polarization error plot is shown in Fig. 4b. The difference is within ± 5 dB for the majority of the bistatic receiver range, excluding differences in null depth and angular location of the nulls.

Fig. 4. (a) Measured and predicted RCS, (b) prediction error for dihedral at 20° pitch, $\phi_t = -10^\circ$ (S2), frequency 10 GHz, HH-polarization.

Finally, the HH-polarization predicted and measured RCS for the dihedral at 20° roll and $\phi_t = -30^\circ$ (S3) is shown in Fig. 5a. The pattern cut for this dihedral orientation follows the same general behavior as the dihedral at 45° pitch (S1); i.e. peak at 30° and significant diffraction behavior for $\phi_r < 20^\circ$. These similarities highlight the difficulty in ATR of identifying small changes in orientation of simple canonical shapes.

Similar results are found for VV-polarization. The VV-polarization plots for the three scenarios are shown in Figures 6-8.

A quantitative summary of the peak mainlobe response, 3 dB mainlobe width, and difference between peak mainlobe and

Fig. 5. (a) Measured and predicted RCS, (b) prediction error for dihedral at 20° roll, and $\phi_t = -30^\circ$ (S3), frequency 10 GHz, HH-polarization.

Fig. 6. (a) Measured and predicted RCS, (b) prediction error for dihedral at 45° pitch, $\phi_t = -30^\circ$ (S1), frequency 10 GHz, VV-polarization.

first sidelobe magnitudes for each of the three scenarios as well as computation times for each prediction method are shown in Table II. Although MoM and FIT predictions both have peak scattering response within 3.2 dB of measurements and mainlobe width predictions within 3.2° , these integral methods require minutes to hours to compute a single azimuthal sweep (200 sample points) at a single frequency. The CPO and PM methods are much faster (on the order of milliseconds) and are still fairly accurate, within 3.8 dB in peak magnitude and 2.9° in mainlobe width. Thus, for many applications, the faster CPO and PM prediction models are preferred. The computational advantage of CPO and PM will further increase as the number of azimuth, elevation, and frequency samples is increased and as the target size increases.

IV. CONCLUSION

The bistatic scattering behavior of a right-angle PEC dihedral at three different target orientations was measured and

compared to predictions from MoM, FIT, SBR, CPO, and PM methods. All six waveforms have similar mainlobe forward scattering responses for each of the three dihedral orientations. Differences are significant in the sidelobe region in some geometries, especially for the simpler, faster CPO and PM predictions. However, since sidelobes are generally windowed in bistatic radar applications, the fast computations of CPO and PM are preferred for bistatic predictions of the dihedral.

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TABLE II
QUANTITATIVE SUMMARY

Scenario 1			
Prediction Method	Peak (dBsm)	3dB Width ($^{\circ}$)	Peak to sidelobe (dB)
	HH-pol, VV-pol	HH-pol, VV-pol	HH-pol, VV-pol
Measure	1.9, 0.8	11.25 $^{\circ}$, 12.6 $^{\circ}$	13.9, 11.37
CPO	2.2, 2.9	14.2 $^{\circ}$, 13.7 $^{\circ}$	14.0, 15.7
SBR	2.2, 2.9	14.2 $^{\circ}$, 13.6 $^{\circ}$	14.1, 15.7
FIT	0.6, 3.3	14.3 $^{\circ}$, 12.8 $^{\circ}$	13.0, 13.7
PM	4.5, 4.5	10.9 $^{\circ}$, 10.9 $^{\circ}$	15.0, 15.0
MoM	0.7, 1.9	14.5 $^{\circ}$, 13.6 $^{\circ}$	12.9, 12.5

Scenario 2			
Prediction Method	Peak (dBsm)	3dB Width ($^{\circ}$)	Peak to sidelobe (dB)
	HH-pol, VV-pol	HH-pol, VV-pol	HH-pol, VV-pol
Measure	0.2, 0.2	11.4 $^{\circ}$, 10.5 $^{\circ}$	13.4, 13.3
CPO	0.2, -2.3	10.5 $^{\circ}$, 10.6 $^{\circ}$	13.1, 13.8
SBR	0.4, -2.0	10.5 $^{\circ}$, 10.6 $^{\circ}$	13.2, 13.8
FIT	2.4, -3.0	10.4 $^{\circ}$, 10.5 $^{\circ}$	14.2, 11.0
PM	-0.7, -0.7	10.0 $^{\circ}$, 10.0 $^{\circ}$	13.6, 13.6
MoM	1.5, -3.2	10.8 $^{\circ}$, 10.4 $^{\circ}$	12.5, 13.5

Scenario 3			
Prediction Method	Peak (dBsm)	3dB Width ($^{\circ}$)	Peak to sidelobe (dB)
	HH-pol, VV-pol	HH-pol, VV-pol	HH-pol, VV-pol
Measure	-1.0, 0.2	11.9 $^{\circ}$, 11.6 $^{\circ}$	11.3, 13.3
CPO	1.6, 1.5	11.9 $^{\circ}$, 12.1 $^{\circ}$	13.3, 14.1
SBR	-0.1, -0.1	11.6 $^{\circ}$, 11.8 $^{\circ}$	12.8, 13.8
FIT	-0.3, 0.8	12.2 $^{\circ}$, 12.0 $^{\circ}$	12.4, 13.4
PM	2.8, 2.8	12.1 $^{\circ}$, 12.1 $^{\circ}$	14.2, 14.2
MoM	0.2, 0.9	11.4 $^{\circ}$, 11.7 $^{\circ}$	14.5, 13.2

Prediction Method	Computation Time
Measure	Order(hours)
CPO	Order(milliseconds)
SBR	Order(seconds)
FIT	Order(hours)
PM	Order(milliseconds)
MoM	Order(minutes)

Fig. 7. (a) Measured and predicted RCS, (b) prediction error for dihedral at 20 $^{\circ}$ pitch, $\phi_t = -10^{\circ}$ (S2), frequency 10 GHz, VV-polarization.

Fig. 8. (a) Measured and predicted RCS, (b) prediction error for dihedral at 20 $^{\circ}$ roll, and $\phi_t = -30^{\circ}$ (S3), frequency 10 GHz, VV-polarization.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. T. Ruck, Ed., *Radar Cross Section Handbook*. New York: Plenum Press, 1970.
- [2] J. W. Crippin Jr. and K. M. Siegel, *Methods of Radar Cross-Section Analysis*. New York: Academic Press, 1968.
- [3] T. Griesser and C. A. Balanis, "Backscatter analysis of dihedral corner reflectors using physical optics and physical theory of diffraction," *IEEE Trans. on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 1137–1147, Oct. 1987.
- [4] ———, "Dihedral corner reflector backscatter using higher order reflections and diffractions," *IEEE Trans. on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 35, no. 11, pp. 1235–1247, Nov. 1987.
- [5] J. A. Jackson, "Closed-form, bistatic 3D scattering solution for a dihedral corner reflector," in *Progress in Electromagnetics Research Symposium (PIERS), PIERS Online*, vol. 6, no. 5, 2010, pp. 495–499.
- [6] J. A. Jackson, B. D. Rigling, and R. L. Moses, "Canonical scattering feature models for 3D and bistatic SAR," *IEEE Trans. on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 525–541, Apr. 2010.
- [7] C. A. Balanis, *Advanced Engineering Electromagnetics*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1989.
- [8] A. K. Bhattacharyya and D. L. Sengupta, *Radar Cross Section Analysis and Control*. Norwood, MA: Artech House, 1991.
- [9] T. Weiland, "Time domain electromagnetic field computation with finite difference methods," *International Journal of Numerical Modelling*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 295–319, Jul. 1996.
- [10] J. Baldauf, S.-W. Lee, L. Lin, S.-K. Jeng, S. Scarborough, and C. Yu, "High frequency scattering from trihedral corner reflectors and other benchmark targets: SBR versus experiment," *Antennas and Propagation, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 39, no. 9, pp. 1345–1351, Sep. 1991.
- [11] J. A. Jackson, *Three-Dimensional Feature Models for Synthetic Aperture Radar and Experiments in Feature Extraction*. The Ohio State University: Ph.D. Dissertation, 2009.
- [12] E. F. Knott, J. F. Shaeffer, and M. T. Tuley, *Radar Cross Section, Second Edition*. Boston: Artech House, 1993.